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Service Delivery in Tertiary Institutions in Nigeria: Problems and Way Forward

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***Abstract:** The purpose of this study is to identify and analyze the barriers to service delivery in tertiary institutions in Nigeria. This study examined the factors that hindered the smooth delivery of services in these institutions in Nigeria. The paper is a review paper that depend on secondary data. The secondary data were collected from print and online publications. The paper identified poor funding, shortage of infrastructure facilities, shortage of office stationaries, poor training of staff, and shortage of staff, corruption, weak regulatory agencies, brain-drain and weak tertiary institutions managers as barriers to effective service delivery in the tertiary institutions in Nigeria. Based on this, the paper recommends that there should be increment in the budgetary allocation of public tertiary institutions by the government, provision of adequate infrastructure facilities, office stationaries, staff training and, employment of adequate staff and motivation of staff to curtain brain-drain. Public institution like the SERVICOM should be reformed and funded well to be able to improve service delivery in the various tertiary institutions. Technology should be deployed to curtain corruption by the managers of tertiary institutions in Nigeria. Competent managers should be appointed to manage the various tertiary institutions to help in the improvement of the quality in the system.*

***Key words:** Service Delivery, Tertiary Institutions.*

1.0 Introduction

Tertiary education is an organized educational system that is consciously designed for manpower production, in-service training and national development. Tertiary education is an education that advances teaching, research and community services for national development. Tertiary education is an education industry that is meant for the production of manpower and national development via implementation of teaching, research and provision of community services (2025). Tertiary education

is an educational institution that is saddled with the responsibilities of teaching, research and community service implementation for manpower development and nation-building (Ogunode, Awah & Suleiman, 2024). Tertiary education, also called post-secondary education, is any level of education pursued beyond high school, including undergraduate and graduate credentials. These credentials encompass certificates, diplomas or academic degrees. Tertiary education refers to specialized education in a specific field, taken on after finishing high school. Tertiary education is non-compulsory and provided in a specialist institution, usually a college, polytechnic or university. This form of education may be delivered virtually or at a distance (Top-hat, 2023). According to Edinoh & Wali-Essien (2023), tertiary education is a social agent of progress and development in the society and aids technological advancement. It is designed to help in the development of nations by providing the high as well as the middle level manpower needed for the social, economic and political advancement through the programme of teaching, learning, research and community services.

Tertiary education prepares the individual for the world of work with a study of the proper theories and relevant hands –on experience. The curriculum of tertiary institutions is developed to ensure that students can meet the challenges of the workplace and also ensure that all the relevant materials necessary for this are available for effective training and experience (Mgboji, Uzoegwu, & Onah, n.d in Musa, 2022). The objectives of tertiary education includes; to provide higher education opportunities via effective teaching, researching and provision community services; to develop produce students with specialized knowledge and skills for solving personal problem and national problem; to prepare student for national workforce and to contribute to societal and community development; to provide academic program of various disciplines; to provide quality instruction in field of studies and to conduct researches to generate new knowledge for national development and to solve complex problems (Ogunode, 2025).

Tertiary institutions are structured to provide services. The services includes; academic services and community services. The academic staff and the non-academic staff are saddled with the responsibilities in the tertiary institutions to provide the services. The academic staff according Ogunode (2025) is an individual that is employed in a higher institution to provide the services of teaching, research and community services. Academic staff is a professional engaged in the tertiary institutions to provide academic services that includes teaching, researching and provision of community services. The job functions of an academic staff includes; pres entation of lectures, preparation of lecture plan, organization of instructional resources, students assessment, project supervision, script making, record keeping, committee assignment, supervision of examination and practical work execution. The non-academic staff or administrative staff according to (Madukoma & Opeke, 2013) are senior non-academic or senior administrative staff who occupy different positions and play different roles in the university. Non-academic staff members are strong members of higher institutions. The non-academic staff handles the day-to-day administration and operations of the university. The non-academic staff perform mainly administrative as well as technical duties. The non-academic staff occupies important offices in the university environment. The non-academic staffs function in the following departments within the university: The registry, maintenance, vice-chancellor's office, deputy vice-chancellor's office, bursary, student affairs, human resources/establishments, cafeteria, security, venture and bookshop among others (Madukoma et al 2013). The roles of the non-academic staff in the administration and management of the universities cannot be overstated because they function in all the units, departments and faculties (Ogunode et al.,2020)

The academic staff offices and services of academic staff are been performed in the faculties, departments and colleges and the services are mainly academic staff while the non-academic department in a university system consists of works, bursary, librarian, medical personnel, exams and records, confidential secretaries, cleaners/messengers, administrative staff, account, security personnel among others.

Iwuoha, (2018) noted that many of these departments are greatly inefficient at their capacity to function effectively and support the university system to achieve its stated objectives and goals especially in state and federal universities in Nigeria. For instance, exams and record department in Nigerian universities have a long history and mismanagement of student's results and preparing academic transcripts for students. This inefficiency has gone so deep to an extent where foreign universities or organizations will send a mail to exams and records department to confirm a student's academic status and will not get any response. Furthermore, a student will be processed for National Youth Service Corp (NYSC) and when the student comes back to request for his/her academic transcript, that when the exams and record department will found out that the students have a missing result. Additionally, the bursary department will allocate a project or work to a contractor and bring up different stories and the issue of no funds after job completion. Furthermore, the department of works is seen as a department filled with incompetent staff who cannot successfully carry out a task especially with regard to employees who uses low-quality materials to execute a task (Samuel and Chipunza, 2009). Poor services delivery appear to be prevalence in Nigeria' tertiary institutions especially among the academic staff and non-academic staff of most federal and state tertiary institutions in Nigeria especially when it comes to academic and administrative services. It is based on this that this paper seeks to discuss the barriers to service delivery in tertiary institutions in Nigeria

2.0 Literatures Review

2.1 Concept of Service Delivery

Service delivery simply refers to the delivery of a service from a business to a customer. The service a business provides is something that the customer is unable to perform themselves, so there are a lot of elements to good service delivery. Service delivery is one of the most important aspects of running a business. It provides the opportunity to impress customers and show them what the business can do and the value it offers. This can create an excellent relationship with the customer and lead to good reviews and word-of-mouth marketing. In this article, we look at what service delivery is, why it matters and examples of different service providers. Service delivery simply refers to the delivery of a service from a business to a customer. The service a business provides is something that the customer is unable to perform themselves, so there are a lot of elements to good service delivery. It encompasses all aspects of providing a service to a customer, including the initial interaction, onboarding, set up, conclusion of the service and follow-up provisions (Indeed editorial team 2024). Service delivery is a concept that has an elegant word for getting goods and services to people in a way that meets their expectations. Service delivery is crucial for the public sector too, as part of government social contract with citizens. Service delivery priorities in development include material infrastructure like roads, power grids, health care, education, water systems, and social protection (Karim, 2015). According to Oronsaye (2010) public service delivery can be seen as "the process of meeting the needs of citizens through prompt and efficient procedures." This implies that the interaction between government and citizens are such that the needs of the citizens are met in a timely manner, thereby making the citizens key in public service delivery. The implication here is that as the private sector considers its customer as „king“, thereby ensuring quality service delivery, the public should be regarded as „master“ and the beneficiary of enhanced performance of the public service (Aladegbola &Jaiyeola, 2016).

Service delivery in the tertiary institutions are anchored on academic services and supportive academic services. Academic service means an academic activity or project undertaken to provide services to society/community. It is an activity/project that is carried out according to the aptitude in the field that the institute has the expertise to help, develop, and strengthen community/social sustainability. In addition, academic service is an integrated activity. In order to provide academic service to operate effectively, the institute encourages all lecturers and students to apply the knowledge gained from learning and teaching both in principle, theory, and practice in providing academic services to the community and society at the provincial level and national level. Along with monitoring, evaluating, and applying the results of academic services that have been analyzed and developed the appropriate body of knowledge further. Moreover, the results create positive changes for communities and internal organizations in areas such as value creation, knowledge, etc., and also build enabling the community/society to be self-reliant according to their own potential and create a force to drive society according to the master plan of the national strategy (TRSU 2020). The Academic Service according to EUI (2025) oversees and supports various academic processes, including the application, selection, and admission of Master's students, Doctoral and Postdoctoral researchers, fellows, and professors. The Service acts as the University Registrar and manages the academic progress of Master's students and Doctoral researchers throughout their programmes. This is done in close collaboration with the academic units and the Dean of Graduate Studies (EUI (2025)).

The major function of tertiary institutions service is to provide services; provide enabling environment for economic growth and prosperity for citizens as well as securing and strengthening democratic institutions. The academic services includes; academic services, community services, research services, teaching service, supervision of project services, record keeping services, mentoring and advising services, exclusion service. The supportive services that are provided by non-academic staff includes; counselling services, medical services, transport service, library services, ICT services, security services, education services, hostel service, administrative services, sport services, maintenance services, students services.

Services in the tertiary institutions includes; counselling services, medical services, transport service, library services, ICT services, academic services, community services, research services, security services, education services, teaching service, hostel service, administrative services, sport services, maintenance services and students services. From the above, Service delivery refers to the process of providing a service or product to a client or customer. It includes all the activities and processes involved in fulfilling a customer's needs or requirements. This can include things like product delivery, customer support, and other services that are necessary to ensure the satisfaction of the customer. Service delivery can vary depending on the industry and type of service being offered, but the end goal is always the same - to provide a high-quality service that meets the customer's expectations and needs. In an academic environment, service delivery is the purely educational services delivery that includes courses, lectures, and workshops. This aspect of service delivery is especially important in higher education, where the quality of service can greatly impact the learning experience of students.

3.0 Method

Because of the nature of this paper, Verstelien tradition method is adopted, whereby data collection is not based on pre-determined variables linked to a stated hypothesis. Instead emphasis is on generation of insight and understanding of the subject matter through description. Therefore this research adopts descriptive method. The sources of data are majorly secondary, sources like documentary research materials, official papers, journals, textbooks, library and archival materials and Internet sources (adapted from Ajao, 2010).

4.0 Data analysis on Barriers to Services Delivery in Tertiary Institution in Nigeria

There are many barriers to effective service delivery in public tertiary institutions in Nigeria. The barriers includes; poor funding, shortage of infrastructure facilities, shortage of stationaries, poor training, shortage of staff, corruption, weak regulatory agencies, brain-drain and weak tertiary institutions managers

Poor funding

Poor funding of tertiary institutions in Nigeria is a challenge to effective service delivery in the various institutions. Higher institutions especially the universities rely mostly on the government for funding. The low per capita income of most Nigerians also affected the government funding ability of these institutions. Funding university education has been a chronic problem on which several scholars have commented. (Akinkugbe, 2001 and Shehu, 2005). Under funding and inadequate financial resources among other factors are the major constraints to effective service delivery in tertiary institutions in Nigeria (Ogunode, & Onyekachi, 2023). Funds are needed to procure both human and materials resources required to provide quality services in the institutions. The non-availability of these funds will resulted to poor services delivery in the various institutions across Nigeria. The major issue in educational development is shortage of funds. One of the most serious problems threatening the survival of the educational systems is that of dwindling level of public funding in the face of rising demands and hence rising cost of higher education. This shortage of funds affects job performance and the growth of the institution. Higher educational institutions cannot perform optimally without funding. This situation calls for increased fund initiative from both the government and educational stakeholders so as to sustain the tempo and growth of education industry (Akinfolarin & Gabriel, 2014). Poor funding of tertiary institutions is responsible for poor services delivery in the various institutions (Egu, Ogbonna, Obike, & Obiuto, 2014).

Shortage of infrastructure facilities

Shortage of infrastructure facilities in the tertiary institutions is also contributing to the poor service delivery in the various tertiary institutions in Nigeria. Apart from the teacher and students inputs, another equally important component aiding effective service delivery is the quantity and quality of physical and material resource available and deployed. This is because the operations of staff and students will be worthless if adequate preparation is not made for relevant facilities, equipments and materials to be made available when they are needed by the users. Uche, Okoli and Ahunanya (2011) and Omale, Ojo, Ibrahim, & Yusufu, 2023) stated that infrastructural facilities and physical environment give educational institutions their appropriate shape and support service delivery in the areas of teaching and learning. These facilities portray the quality of the institution in terms of their staff/students friendliness, attraction to outsiders, aesthetics, healthy, safe, currency and relevance. Material resources in the University refer mainly to many of the non-consumable materials. They are also the physical infrastructural facilities provided in the University for research and teaching. Material resources include all the structures as well as machines, laboratory equipment, the chalkboard and other tools of the lecturer. They include all infrastructural facilities, which are usually put into educational use like furniture, laboratories, laboratory equipment and materials, classrooms, library, studios and the space within the premises of an educational institution Fadipe's diary (as cited in Alani, 2011; Ishaya & Ogunode, 2021). The shortage of these facilities in the tertiary institutions affects service delivery and implementation of curriculum in the tertiary institutions (Akinfolarin, & Gabriel, 2014).

Shortage of stationaries

Another factor contribution to poor service delivery in the tertiary institutions in Nigeria is shortage of office stationary. Ogunode and Abubakar (2020) submitted that lack of adequate working tools is another problem facing the majority of Nigerian public tertiary institutions and this is affecting the quality of service delivery in the institutions.. Working tools or office equipment like Stapler, Eraser, Push-pin, Drawing pin (U.K)/ Thumbtack (U.S), Paper clip, Rubber stamp, Highlighter, Fountain pen Pencil, Marker, Ballpoint, Bulldog clip, Tape dispenser, Pencil sharpener, Label, Calculator, Glue, Scissors, Sticky notes, 4A Paper, Notebook, Envelope, Clipboard, Monitor, Computer, Keyboard, Folder, Fax, Filing cabinet, Telephone, Swivel chair, Desk, Wastebasket, printer and calculators are inadequate in many students' affairs units, bursary department, VC offices, Registrar offices and academic affairs units across the various higher institutions. The inability of the institutions of higher learning to provide these materials in quantities and quality is affecting the quality of services delivery to the stakeholder of the institutions (Ogunode, 2020).

Poor training

Another barriers to effective services delivery in the tertiary institutions in Nigeria is the problem of poor training of both academic and non-academic staff. The poor training has contributed to poor services delivery in many higher institutions in Nigeria especially among the non-academic staff. The inefficiency according to Adejare, Olaore, Udofia, Emola (2020) among non-academic staff units such as exams and records, works and bursary among others are regarded to be lack of effective training and development and sometimes due to wrong placement and recruitment of staff. Training and development as it is said that is an essential tool necessary for organization growth and survival especially in a dynamic and ever-changing business environment. Training and development are important for a university administrator to be effective and efficient at the work they do for the organization. This means that lack of training and development of university administrators would hinder the success and educational services of a university system and this would affect the rating and attraction of the university to the international community. Notably, inefficient training and development of employees among state and federal university administrators in Nigeria are attributed to lack of strategic career planning and growth, lack of adequate infrastructural facility and inadequate tools for employees to effectively perform at work (Diefendorff et al., 2018). Poor training programme in the universities have affected the rate at which both academic and non-academic staff delivery the teaching and research services (Olowonefa, Ogunode, & Ohibime 2022; Oludayo, 2021; Oluremi. & Oyewole, 2014; Bala, 2013).

Shortage of staff

The shortage of staff which include both academic staff and non-academic staff in the Nigerian' tertiary institutions is a very strong factors that has contributed to poor service delivery in the institutions. The academic staff according to Ogunode (2025) is the curriculum implementer and the non-academic staff of a tertiary institution is the support system through which the success of the academician and students in a tertiary institutions relies upon. Most Nigerian tertiary institutions are experiencing inefficiency and unproductivity among their staff and this is due to high workload (Ng'ethe, Iravo and Namusonge, 2012).

Okunola (2007) identified the challenge of shortage in lecturer number in universities, and how it affects service delivery in the teaching and learning process. Balogun in European Commission (2019) was more succinct in his analysis of lecturer shortage in Nigerian universities. He categorized lecturer inadequacies in four groups viz: overt shortage of lecturers; hidden shortages; suppressed shortages

and modern shortages. He noted that actual vacancies to be filled is overt shortages; positions filled by unqualified lecturers who teach outside their area of specialization are hidden shortages; suppressed shortage is seen as relating to lack of pedagogical training required in teaching while modern shortage is used to describe lecturers who are qualified but are out of touch with current development in their fields. Also, Ogunode et al (2022) and Ekundayo, and Kolawole (2013) lamented how shortage of non-academic staff in some tertiary institutions in Nigeria is affecting the quality of service delivery. Emiko, (2023) noted poor services delivery in the Bursary departments and student affairs is mostly due to shortage of staff. The number of staff in those units and department are not adequate to service the number of students coming for various academic services.

Corruption

Corruption in the management of tertiary institutions in Nigeria is another critical factors hampering effective service delivery in the tertiary institutions across Nigeria. Igbuzor, (2017) noted that corruption is widespread and endemic in Nigeria. But we know that the problem of corruption is as old as society itself and cuts across nations, cultures, races and classes of people. It is undoubtedly one of the greatest challenges of our times leading to underdevelopment and poor service delivery in Nigeria. Corruption has a lot of negative consequences on every sphere of societal development whether social, economic or political. Corruption not only leads to poor service delivery but loss of lives. Corruption is pervasive in Nigeria with serious negative consequences. Despite the plethora of legislations and agencies fighting corruption in the country, corruption has remained widespread and pervasive because of failure to utilize universally accepted and tested strategies; disconnect between posturing of leaders and their conduct; lack of concrete sustainable anti-corruption programming and failure to locate the anti-corruption struggle within a broader struggle to transform society. Corruption in the administration of higher education in Nigeria is responsible for shortage of facilities, shortage of staff, poor quality education and poor services delivery (Nwaokugha, Nyewusira, & Nyewusira, 2013; Nwankwo, & Nweke, 2016; Nwaokugha, & Ezeugwu, 2017). Corruption have hampered development of education and specifically responsible for low development in tertiary institutions in Nigeria (Ogunode & Stephen, 2021; Ogunode, Josiah, & Ajape, 2021)

Weak regulatory agencies

Weak regulatory agencies of the federal and state government that are to ensure quality services are delivered to the students and stakeholders in the institutions. Over the years, there has been poor service delivery by the public sector in Nigeria leading to the launch of the Nigeria Service Delivery Initiative by the former President Olusegun Obasanjo, GCFR in March, 2014. The Federal Government signed a social compact with all Nigerians (SERVICOM) to improve citizen satisfaction by promoting service excellence in Public Service. Igbuzor, (2017) maintained that in an effort to meet the expectations of the people and as part of the Federal governments' reform agenda, the Service Delivery Initiative (SDI) was launched conceptualized as a social contract between the Federal Government and all Nigerians: Service Compact with all Nigerians (SERVICOM). SERVICOM gives the Nigerian people the right to demand good service as entitlements, contained in SERVICOM charters reflecting the mission and vision statements of each government department along with goals, objectives, details of services, standards of performance as well as system of redress should there be service failure (National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy (NEEDS 2)(2007). Unfortunately, the present state of the public service can neither deliver services to meet the expectations above nor to the standards expected by SERVICOM for several reasons including lack of capacity, poor orientation and attitude, weak incentives, weak monitoring and evaluation system and

corruption. This is why there is the need for a comprehensive and holistic reform of the public service (Igbuzor, 2017).

Brain-drain

Brain-drain is a major challenge to effective service delivery in the tertiary institutions in Nigeria. Ogunode (2020) defined Brain-drain as the movement of professionals from developing countries to developed countries for a better job offers. Brain-drain is a situation whereby professional individuals are migrating from their countries to another country to seek greener pasture. Many lecturers and researchers are leaving public universities in Nigeria to other part of African countries and Europe for a better job offer and conducive working environment. The mass movement of professionals from the various tertiary institutions in Nigeria have negative impact on the service delivery in the institutions (Ohiare Udebu, Ogunode & Rauf 2021; Okoli, Ogbondah, & Ewor, 2016). The teaching, research and communities services are mostly affected by brain-drain problems in the institutions (Ifeyinwa & Okemute, 2023). This has led to high students –lecturer’ ratio.

Weak tertiary institutions managers

Leaders in some universities are weak, uncoordinated and lack administrative skills. Some do not have administrative knowledge or skills. According to Ekaette in Ogunode (2020) a lot of higher education system managers do not poses the charisma, or good human relations needed for effective and efficient leadership. As a result of the poor leadership and ineffective style of administration, a lot of programme of activities are not carried out in such institutions such as provision of grant for research and publications, staff welfare is neglected, no adequate control of staff and students, no vision for the University. Such leaders also do not have the zeal for supervision and monitoring of institutional activities. This can affect the systems performance in that, workers can result to a non-chalant attitude toward work and hence no sustainability or continuity of good track records of performance in the system. Nigerian Higher Educational System need leaders who can position it to an envying height of success and progress this contributing to society’s quest for self-reliance Ujomu in Ogunode 2020).

a. Findings

The paper showed that poor funding, shortage of infrastructure facilities, shortage of office stationaries, poor training of staff, shortage of staff, corruption, weak regulatory agencies, brain-drain and weak tertiary institutions managers are the barriers to effective service delivery in the tertiary institutions in Nigeria.

b. Conclusion and Recommendation

This paper examined the barriers to services delivery in the tertiary institutions in Nigeria. The paper identified poor funding, shortage of infrastructure facilities, shortage of office stationaries, poor training of staff, shortage of staff, corruption, weak regulatory agencies, brain-drain and weak tertiary institutions managers as barriers to effective service delivery in the tertiary institutions in Nigeria.

Based on this, the paper recommends that there should be increment in the budgetary allocation of public tertiary institutions by the government, provision of adequate infrastructure facilities, office stationaries, staff training, employment of adequate staff and motivation of staff to curtain brain-drain. Public institution like the SERVICOM should be reformed and funded well to be able to improve service delivery in the various tertiary institutions. Technology should be deployed to curtain corruption by the managers of tertiary institutions in Nigeria. Competent managers should be appointed to manage the various tertiary institutions to help in the improvement of the quality in the system.

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